

The Battle between Greed and the Preservation of the Earth

Amazon Book Review Series of “*Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*”

KSMO

January 7, 2025

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The future of our existence is sadly tethered to the battle between greed and the preservation of the earth. This book delves deep into common sense and explains how the fragile cycle of all life can be sustained with appropriate measures. Since the beginning of time, countless millenniums before mankind, all life has co-existed together to sustain the cycle. Still, now it's competing in a battle for survival, which has looked dire since the evolution of mankind. The epilogue says it all, and it's scary. An eye-opener!

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★★★★★ A no brainer survival guide

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Screenshot. Review of “*Better Economics for the Earth*” by KSMO [1]. Reviewed in the United States on January 7, 2025.

(*) Note: This paper reprints KSMO’s review [1] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [2].

References

[1] KSMO. (2025, Jan. 7). A no brainer survival guide.

<https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R1G4VKXQWSS3MS/>

[2] Vuong, Q. H. & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>